

DOING JUSTICE COLLECTIVE

DIALOGUES ON JUSTICE:

A CARD DECK TO GUIDE JUSTICE CIRCLE PRACTICE

IMPRINT

Authors

Doing Justice Collective (<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3655-0116>)

Jules Rochielle Sievert (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0434-2254>)

Hernán Felipe Bobadilla Rodriguez (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0003-9952>)

Stefanie Burkhart (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5539-3927>)

Franziska Ehnert (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4611-7242>)

Marina Novikova (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8041-0442>)

Eveline Wandl-Vogt (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0802-0255>)

How to cite this document (cite as)

Doing Justice Collective, Sievert, J. R., Bobadilla Rodriguez, H. F., Burkhart, S., Ehnert, F., Novikova, M., Wandl-Vogt, E., 2026: Dialogues on justice: a card deck to guide justice circle practice. 10.5281/zenodo.20424942.

Available at

10.5281/zenodo.20424942

Copyright notice

© Jules Rochielle Sievert, Hernán Felipe Bobadilla Rodriguez, Stefanie Burkhart, Franziska Ehnert, Marina Novikova, Eveline Wandl-Vogt, 2026

This publication is published under a Creative Commons Attribution - ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0) licence (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>).

Publication date 01.06.2026

Graphic Design © Ulrike Schinke, Kerstin Ludewig

Printing optimized for Format DIN A6 (105 mm x 148 mm)

Acknowledgements

We want to thank the participants of the workshop session “From Unspoken to Outspoken: Making voices heard and practicing justice in transdisciplinary and transformative research” at the ITD Alliance Conference 2024 “Inter- and Transdisciplinarity Beyond Buzzwords” and of the Summer School 2025 “Justice in an Interlinked World: Revisiting rural-urban and South-North relationships” for their feedback on the Justice Circle Practice and their encouragement to nourish and share this practice. We want to extend a special thanks to Ulrike Schinke and Kerstin Ludewig for their support in designing the card deck.

INTRODUCTION

This card deck is a tool designed to help researchers and societal actors engage with issues of justice – especially in the context of **transdisciplinary and transformative research (TTR)** - through a shared basic understanding and guiding questions. It assumes a diverse audience with varied disciplinary backgrounds and life experiences, creating conditions for fruitful discussion, exchange, exploration, and reflection.

The deck is organized into four main categories:

- First, **dimension cards** introduce broad, abstract aspects of justice to be examined and assessed in the context of a project.

- Second, **concept cards** present notions that are relevant to issues of justice and help articulate perspectives and opinions.
- Third, **approach cards** outline frameworks for addressing justice from distinctive, although often flexible, angles.
- Finally, **thematic and domain-specific cards** explore justice through focused concerns or disciplinary lenses.

Users may engage with some of the categories or all of them, depending on the nature of the problems at hand.

STRUCTURE

Categories

Dimensions of justice

Specification

Distributional justice

Procedural justice

Recognitional justice

Concepts of justice

Intersectionality

Capabilities

Spatiality

Temporality

Approaches to justice

Epistemic justice

Restorative justice

Affirmative justice &
Transformative justice

Thematic and domain-specific understandings of justice

Environmental justice

Energy justice

Food justice

Health justice

DISTRIBUTIONAL JUSTICE

Distributional justice focuses on the fair allocation of costs and benefits across society. It plays a central role in addressing inequities and is essential for shaping policies and practices that promote a more equitable society. It often considers the needs, merits, and contributions of individuals and groups, and may also extend beyond humans to include the costs and benefits of the natural environment.

Questions for Applying Distributive Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can a research project be managed and resources be allocated to advance distributive justice?
2. How can these resources be distributed to ensure that all stakeholders share the costs and benefits fairly?
3. How can we address historical and structural inequities in TTR to elevate underrepresented voices in the distribution of research outcomes?

RECOGNITIONAL JUSTICE

Recognitional justice

focuses on the acknowledgment and respect of diverse identities, cultures, knowledge systems, and experiences. This implies the recognition of underlying systemic injustices. It relates to both humans – recognising how different values, preferences, and needs are rooted in different histories, identities, cultural backgrounds and epistemologies - and other species – recognising the intrinsic value of nature. Recognitional justice ensures that all humans and more-than human species are valued and represented equally.

Questions for Applying Recognitional Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we create spaces that respect and uplift the diverse voices of all participants, ensuring they feel seen, heard, and valued throughout the research process?
2. How can we ensure that the knowledge, values and cultural practices of diverse groups are fully recognized and integrated into the research process?
3. How can we address and rectify historical misrepresentations or exclusions of certain identities and experiences in both the design and dissemination of research?

PROCEDURAL JUSTICE

Procedural justice concerns the fairness, transparency, and inclusiveness of the processes, institutions, and practices of decision-making. It emphasises the rights and abilities of individuals and communities to engage in shaping decisions that impact their lives and environments. Central to procedural justice is the co-creation of processes that reflect diverse experiences, dismantle power imbalances, and ensure that participation is not only possible but also valued and effective. By fostering collaboration, transparency, and shared ownership, procedural justice strengthens the legitimacy, trust, and equity of outcomes in research and decision-making.

Questions for Applying Procedural Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can TTR methodologies ensure that all participants, especially marginalised and vulnerable groups, have equal and meaningful opportunities to shape decision-making processes?
2. How can we promote transparency and accountability throughout the research process to build trust among stakeholders?
3. How can we design feedback and power-sharing mechanisms to support inclusive participation and shared ownership of research outcomes?

INTERSECTIONALITY

Intersectionality is a framework for understanding how multiple social identities – such as race, gender, class, sexuality, and ability - intersect and create unique experiences of privilege or oppression. It emphasizes that individuals and communities are shaped by multiple, overlapping systems of power and inequality (e.g. racism, sexism, ableism, colonialism), which cannot be fully understood in isolation from one another. Intersectionality is essential for examining how these factors contribute to complex, compounded injustices.

Questions for Applying Intersectionality in TTR Approaches:

1. Whose (intersecting) identities and lived experiences are centred or excluded in TTR and how can we ensure their equal participation to meet different needs?
2. How do systems of power (e.g. racism, sexism, ableism, colonialism) shape the research process, participation, and interpretation of data?
3. How does TTR challenge or reproduce social inequalities across multiple axes of identity?

SPATIAL JUSTICE

Spatial justice explores the interconnectedness of (in)justices and spatial environments. It critically examines the relationship between social equity and the spatial configuration of communities, infrastructures and resources. The idea of *spatiality of injustice* seeks to discern (in)justices in space, while the idea of *injustice of spatiality* seeks to illustrate how (in)justices can be reproduced through space. Spatial justice seeks to foster inclusive spaces where justice is both upheld and expressed tangibly.

Questions for Applying Spatial Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we explore the ways in which spatial arrangements shape social equity, particularly for vulnerable and marginalised groups?
2. How can we address the historical entanglements of space and social inequalities that have contributed to the exclusion of vulnerable groups and more-than-human perspectives, and how can these be reimagined to promote inclusivity?
3. How can we integrate the understanding of how spaces and social inequalities are interconnected to promote spatial justice for all communities?

CAPABILITIES

The *Capabilities Approach* focuses on expanding what individuals and communities are able to do and be, emphasizing real freedoms, opportunities, and well-being rather than simply access to resources. It seeks to empower people – especially vulnerable and marginalised groups – to lead lives they have reason to value. In TTR, this means addressing structural barriers, fostering inclusion, and designing processes that enhance participants' ability to engage meaningfully and sustainably. Recognizing that capabilities vary, research should aim to support equitable development by creating conditions that enable all stakeholders to realize their potential.

Questions for Applying the Capabilities Approach in TTR:

1. How can we design TTR to expand the real freedoms and opportunities of participants, particularly those from marginalised and vulnerable communities?
2. How can we ensure research participants have real opportunities to make choices about how they engage in the research process and articulate their own valued capabilities and aspirations?
3. How can we move beyond traditional outcomes to focus on how research enhances participants' long-term well-being and ability to lead fulfilling lives?

TEMPORAL JUSTICE

Temporal justice

emphasizes fairness in how decisions today impact both present and future generations - both human and more-than-human species. It addresses the responsibility to avoid actions that harm future generations while acknowledging the long-lasting effects of past injustices on the present. This concept calls for thoughtful consideration of how policies, environmental practices, and social systems affect access to resources, rights, and opportunities over time, ensuring that future generations inherit a world that allows them to thrive.

Questions for Applying Temporal Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we ensure that research outcomes are designed with long-term sustainability in mind, benefiting both present and future generations?
2. How can we address the lingering effects of historical injustices through TTR while ensuring that future generations are considered in today's actions?
3. How can we promote equitable access to resources and opportunities across time, ensuring that the needs of future generations are integrated into present-day actions?

EPISTEMIC JUSTICE

Epistemic justice refers to fairness in the distribution of knowledge and the recognition of diverse ways of knowing. It seeks to ensure that all individuals, particularly marginalised and vulnerable individuals and groups, are valued as credible knowers and contributors to collective understanding. *Epistemic injustice* occurs when individuals or groups are excluded or undermined in their capacity to participate in knowledge production, often due to prejudice or social bias. Addressing epistemic injustice is crucial to create more inclusive, equitable systems of knowledge.

Questions for Applying Epistemic Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can TTR actively challenge epistemic injustice by ensuring that marginalised voices are recognized and valued as credible sources of knowledge?
2. How can we design TTR to embrace diverse epistemologies, including more-than-human perspectives, and ensure that different ways of knowing and experiencing the world are integrated into the research process?
3. How can we address historical patterns of epistemic injustice, ensuring that previously silenced or excluded groups have opportunities to shape research and contribute to knowledge production?

RESTORATIVE JUSTICE

Restorative justice

focuses on repairing harm caused by past injustices or conflicts. It seeks to create inclusive processes that promote healing, conflict resolution and reconciliation. It seeks to address wrongs by facilitating dialogue between those doing harm and those affected by harm, ensuring that harm is acknowledged and efforts are made to restore relationships and communities. Restorative justice is concerned with creating pathways to healing for *all* involved: humans, other species and ecosystems. Its focus thus extends from protecting to restoring degraded ecosystems.

Questions for Applying Restorative Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we facilitate dialogues that allow harmed communities or individuals to share their experiences and actively participate in the healing process?
2. How can research processes contribute to repairing past harms and fostering reconciliation between stakeholders?
3. How can restorative justice principles be embedded in the resolution of conflicts that may arise during the research process to strengthen trust and promote reconciliation?

AFFIRMATIVE VS. TRANSFORMATIVE JUSTICE

Affirmative justice seeks to correct inequities within the existing system by providing targeted interventions and reforms, such as affirmative action or policy changes. It focuses on mitigating disadvantages without altering the fundamental structures that produce inequality.

Transformative justice, on the other hand, aims to fundamentally change systems and structures that perpetuate inequities, focusing on deep-rooted change. It seeks to create new frameworks that promote long-term, systemic shifts toward fairness and inclusivity, challenging power imbalances and societal norms.

Questions for Applying Affirmative vs. Transformative Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we differentiate between short-term, affirmative measures and long-term, transformative changes when addressing social inequities in research?
2. In what ways can TTR projects aim for transformative justice by challenging the existing structures and systems that perpetuate inequity, rather than simply reforming them?
3. How can affirmative actions in TTR projects serve as stepping stones toward broader, transformative changes, ensuring that both immediate and systemic needs are addressed?

ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

Environmental justice refers to the fair distribution of environmental benefits and burdens across all communities, cultures and species, with a focus on ensuring that marginalised or vulnerable populations are not disproportionately impacted by environmental harm, such as climate change or ecological destruction. It addresses the inequities in exposure to environmental risks, access to natural resources, and decision-making processes that affect environmental policies. Environmental justice advocates for the protection of both, human and more-than-human, emphasizing the need for sustainable practices and policies that promote ecological balance while safeguarding the rights and health of all communities as well as nature itself.

Questions for Applying Environmental Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we ensure that marginalised communities and more-than-human species are not disproportionately impacted by environmental degradation and have equitable access to natural resources?
2. How can we address the intersection of environmental issues with social, economic, and racial inequities in TTR to promote more equitable solutions?
3. How can we contribute to sustainable practices that balance ecological health with social justice through TTR, ensuring that environmental decisions benefit both present and future generations?

HEALTH JUSTICE

Health justice focuses on the fair distribution of healthcare resources, access, and outcomes, ensuring that everyone, regardless of their socio-economic status, race, gender, or location, has the opportunity to achieve optimal health. It addresses the structural inequalities and systemic barriers that lead to health disparities, advocating for policies and practices that prioritize the well-being of marginalised and underserved populations. Health justice is essential for creating an equitable healthcare system that meets the needs of all communities.

Questions for Applying Health Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we integrate the social determinants of health in TTR to better understand and address the root causes of health inequities?
2. How can we contribute to reflecting upon and challenging structural inequalities and systemic barriers that influence the equitable access to healthcare resources?
3. How can TTR methodologies promote health justice by including health and well-being, and by eliminating systemic barriers to care?

ENERGY JUSTICE

Energy justice seeks to ensure the fair distribution of the benefits and burdens of energy systems, including access, affordability, environmental impacts, and decision-making power. It addresses who has energy, who lacks it, and who bears the social and ecological costs of its production and use. Rooted in principles of equity, recognition, and participation, energy justice challenges systemic inequalities while promoting inclusive, sustainable transitions. In TTR, it calls for collaborative approaches that centre marginalised voices, reframe power dynamics, and design energy solutions aligned with social and environmental well-being.

Questions for Applying Energy Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can we ensure that marginalised communities meaningfully shape decisions about energy production, distribution, and governance?
2. How can research projects address and redistribute the social, economic, and environmental burdens of current energy systems?
3. How can TTR methodologies support inclusive energy transitions that prioritize equity, sustainability, and long-term community well-being?

FOOD JUSTICE

Food justice addresses structural inequity and injustice along food supply chains and in food systems. It embraces the idea that food is a human right. Combining the social justice principles of dignity, self-determination, equity, access and participation with environmental justice principles that emphasise distribution, procedure, recognition and further concepts of justice enables a broader and more contemporary understanding of food justice.

Questions for Applying Food Justice in TTR Approaches:

1. How can TTR methodologies help to highlight and reflect upon the injustices along the food supply chains and in food systems in its entirety?
2. How can we engage with and design TTR processes that contribute to repairing historical and structural harms in the food system?
3. How can restorative justice principles be embedded in addressing conflicts over land, resources, and food access to strengthen trust and promote lasting food system change?

Key references:

Justice

Avelino, F., Wijsman, K., Van Steenberghe, F., Jhagroe, S., Wittmayer, J., Akerboom, S., Bogner, K., Jansen, E.F., Frantzeskaki, N., Kalfagianni, A., 2024. Just Sustainability Transitions: Politics, Power, and Prefiguration in Transformative Change Toward Justice and Sustainability. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-112321-081722>

Doing Justice Collective, Beer, K., Felipe Bobadilla Rodriguez, H., Bogner, K., Burkhart, S., Ehnert, F., Hector, V., Herwig, A., Joshi, N., Novikova, M., Rochielle Sievert, J., Wandl-Vogt, E., 2024. Doing Justice! Doing Just This! Practicing justice in transdisciplinary and transformative research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13766955>

European Environment Agency., 2024. Just sustainability transitions: from concept to practice. Publications Office, LU. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2800/6238023>.

Newell, P., Srivastava, S., Naess, L.O., Torres Contreras, G.A., Price, R., 2021. Toward transformative climate justice: An emerging research agenda. *WIREs Climate Change* 12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.733>

Ohlsson, J., Przybylinski, S. (Eds.), 2023. *Theorising justice a primer for social scientists*. Bristol University Press, Bristol, UK.

Circle Practice

Boyes-Watson, C., Pranis, K., 2015. Circle forward: building a restorative school community. Living Justice Press, St. Paul, MN.

Brown, M.A., Di Lallo, S., 2020. Talking Circles: A Culturally Responsive Evaluation Practice. American Journal of Evaluation 41, 367–383.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214019899164>

California Engage. Circle Keeping. URL

<https://californiaengage.org/resource/circle-keeping/>

Institute of Educational Science (IES), 2025. Community-building restorative circles. <https://ies.ed.gov/northwest/2025/01/community-building-restorative-circles>

Mediators Beyond Borders International. Circle process: Restorative circles and community building. URL

<https://mediatorsbeyondborders.org/what-we-do/conflict-literacy-framework/circle-process/>

Montano, S., Williams, V., Tin, J.J., 2022. A Method for Collective Healing: The Utility of Talking Circles. Journal of Multicultural Affairs 8 (1).

<https://scholarworks.sfasu.edu/jma/vol8/iss1/2>

Pranis, K., 2005. Little Book of Circle Processes: A New/Old Approach to Peacemaking. Skyhorse Publishing Company, Incorporated, New York.

Wallace, M.L., 2018. 21st century values inherent in effective circles. International Institute for Restorative Practices.

https://www.iirp.edu/images/conf_downloads/uqYFPV_Values_Inherent_in_Effective_Circles_IIRP.pdf